

The effect of the Internet in learning a language

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Abstract

This article deals with the importance and opportunities of the Internet in a language learning process. It is given that the utilization of the Internet, including networking sites, online platforms for communicating with foreigners provides learners with a good source of manual materials, video lessons and good language learning environment. The benefits and aspects of the information-communicative technologies in educational system is in detail shown. There is no doubt that learning a language with using such kind of technologies is hopefully best way.

Keywords. Effective learning, information-communicative technologies, video and audio lessons, language skills

1. Introduction

These days world is developing day-by-day. The importance of the Internet in every field is significantly increasing, especially in the education system. Students, pupils, all learners, apply to the Internet to find more information, to get knowledge and expand imagination about the thing which is learned.

As for learning a foreign language, by help of the Internet is effective to improve the language skills. On the Internet, there is given online courses, video lessons and the most important thing is that there is a chance to communicate with native speakers to increase the level of speech. Also, the convenience of the Internet is that there is no need to go anywhere for people who are learning online. In addition to this, online lessons are more effective than offline. Learners save their time and money.

All in all, all the benefits of the Internet while studying a foreign language are given in the following groups:

- 1) Learners, who are learning a language by listening to audio or seeing video lessons can rewatch them if they do not understand somewhere.
- 2) The chance of checking knowledge through various tests and determine the level, learn the mistakes which are done.

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3) Other video games which help to improve skills and give energy. Learners are never bored with such kind of games. They have fun with them, also useful information about the topic. One of the most popular game for this is Duo lingo.

4) Daily conversations with native speakers or online foreign friends. This allows people to adapt the language environment and speak freely.

2. Researchers' thoughts about the role of the Internet in learning a language.

With the prevalence of life, attention to the Internet is completely changing. Everybody who has a desire to acquire information about language often considers about information-communication technologies to give more chance to study. In this reason, a lot of researchers in every field have thoroughly studied the advantage sides of online lessons.

The idea of introducing Internet technologies in the course of theoretical and practical classes in a foreign language, according to E. Y. Sokolova, has been widely spread among teachers, methodologists around the world. The didactic aspects of computerization of education have been developed by well-known scientists and educators E. G. Azimov, V. P. Bepalko, B. S. Gershunsky, I. O. Loginov, E. I. Mashbitz, R. P. Mil-rud, E. S. Polat, N. F. Talizina, I. V. Robert, A. V. Khutorskoy and others [10].

The famous American scholar David Crystal in his publication "Language and the Internet" identifies several reasons for the advisability of using the Internet in foreign language teaching [3]. He argues that one reason is that the linguistic nature of online communication is necessary to improve language learning. Another reason for the effectiveness of using the Internet in foreign language teaching, according to the scholar, is that web-based resources create beneficial conditions for writing instruction because online resources provide an audience for written communication. The next reason put forward by David Crystal is that communicating online increases students' motivation to learn a live language several times, and there is a positive effect of the large amount of time students spend online [3].

Conclusion

In conclusion, Internet should be used more in the educational system. This provides us with a great supply of materials which is useful for effective learning. It gives opportunity to have a place in life that after learning a language by using the Internet people can create some sites with their own experiences to be useful for others. It is beneficial for others, also oneself for financial independence.

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